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MODERN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION AND INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

**СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ДОШКОЛЬНОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ
И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ**

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Abstract. Preschool educational institution and innovation is the subject of serious study of modern education. Modern educators of pre-school educational establishments should always be receptive to everything new. Innovations arise when appear to resolve the problem, when it turns out the contradiction between the desire and the actual outcome. The article deals with finding and finding solutions to these problems.

Аннотация. Дошкольные образовательные учреждения и инновационные процессы в них являются предметом серьезного и детального изучения современного процесса образования. Современные педагоги и воспитатели дошкольных образовательных учреждений должны быть восприимчивыми ко всему новому. Инновации возникают тогда, когда появляются возможности и желание разрешить возникшую проблему, когда появляются противоречия между желанием и реальными результатами.

В статье анализируется решение этих проблем в современных условиях.

Keywords: early childhood, education, institution, innovations, processes, teacher, problem.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное, образование, учреждение, инновации, процессы, педагог, проблема.

The first stage of the education system to improving the system of the pre-school education is one of the most pressing issues in our society today. At the same time, the need to upgrade and update the quality of preschool education was high. It is impossible to improve education without undertaking activities like innovative thinking and improving the professionalism of teachers. This situation would have been systematic and consistent in implementing pedagogical innovations. Transformation is characteristic of the world trends. At the same time, the establishment of the Ministry of Pre-School Education in our country, preschool education institutions to their composition it points to the fact that a child's pre-school age is a special focus on education, learning and development. If we think about innovations, there are four types of innovations in science:

- to study support and resistant evidence for innovation;
- research of innovative process. –management of innovative process;
- analyze innovative situations, assess risk and productivity.

Stage of innovative activity designing will be based on the analysis of the quality of educational activities, the development and of the goals objectives of innovation and the development of measures for the implementation of innovative comprehensive programs. The pre-school education institution is designed not only by the uneven working conditions of the educational system, but also by the management system and the pedagogical community, with the goal of achieving a specific goal — the provision of innovation development of the activities of pedagogical staff of pre-school educational institutions should be focused on raising their professional level. The development of pre-school education depends on subjects such as educators, parents and children.

Pedagogical activity the process of innovative learning differs from the traditional teaching process:

–due to rapid changes in technology, content and performance are complex. It requires a pedagogue of special skills and methods of work.

Moreover, the development of modern information technologies puts the additional demand for the quality of its products.

–the peculiarity of the modern pedagogical process with the exception of traditional education, focuses on the child's activity, selection and creativity.

The important function of the educator is to support the child's activities, to help solve problems that arise in front of him:

–It is a requirement of modern education for the interaction of educational subjects to be interesting and active.

The pre-requisites of innovation in pre-school educational institutions, the behavior and potential of the teacher serve as an enthusiasm for the novelty and interest in its implementation. Based on the child's demanding capabilities and, accordingly the development of personal resources a trainee who can change his work can be at the heart of an innovative process.

Achieving productivity when introducing innovation indicates that the trainee has an innovative potential.

The success of implementing these innovations is linked to innovative activity, which is manifested in the subject's personal response to the ongoing changes. The aspiration for innovation goal of innovation high intellectual potential, critical, attitude, all this is manifested by the teachers who aspire to innovative activity.

One of the strategic directions of development of innovation activity in pre-school education is in general.

At the moment, innovative development faces a number of obstacles, increasing the volume of work, lack of resources to implement innovation, material and the weight of educational supplies for children.

It is necessary for the pedagogue to grow professional skills, to improve the research activity, to improve the quality of education for children.

The traditional management system in innovative activities will change, with the administration and pressure drove power, of the educational institution, pedagogues and educator's managers of educational institutions, senior educators, scientific and methodological assistants, the row and the requirements are replaced by other looks.

The real creative potential of the pedagogue is the key to the professional development attitude to work, and the potential for educators.

In particular the analysis of pedagogical practice shows that preschool education to evaluate positive innovations, to develop and implement innovative programs and technologies, and to approach children in terms of quality. There are a number of obstacles in the implementation of innovative technologies: lack of uniform systematization of applied pedagogical innovations, lack of legal normative, scientific and methodological support for pre-school education, pre-school education and examination of innovative educational projects. The need to look for new relationships and attitudes of expertise in quality and effectiveness monitoring. The issues in the world are not the same. To do this, it is necessary to train pedagogues in the pre-school education institutions, which will have an adequate level of innovation activity. The employer must select the targeted educational program and determine the future development of the pre-school education institution based on the community order. The goal is understandable and must be welcomed by all participants in the pedagogical process. At the same time, the administrator must take into consideration the innovation process participant's individual qualities, their professional level, organizational skills and abilities readiness for psychological loading into new activities. Any innovative process is a possible description and its results cannot always be detected. Many can help prevent errors and mistakes and create analytical frameworks and innovative applications at projector model level. Innovative goals and objectives will be too deeply analyze the current situation in the kindergarten, and, on the other hand, to diagnose its development. The overall objective of organizing innovation activities at the pre-school education institution is to achieve a high level of access to the educational system of the kindergarten. There is a high demand for innovations when there is a conflict between the need for a particular approach and the exact outcome and desire to succeed. In conclusion, we can say that the results of the development of innovative activities of pre-school institutions are reflected in the participation of for a particular approach and the exact outcome and desire to succeed.

In conclusion, we can say that the results of the development of innovative activities of pre-school institutions are reflected in the participation of teachers in the renewal of their pre-school education and their participation in author's project, programs, methodological developments in various directions.

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